

A study of kinetics of adsorption of lead and nickel ions on the sawdust of *Cordia africana*

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Abstract : The kinetics of adsorption of lead and nickel ions on the sawdust of *Cordia africana* (lam tree) was studied at room temperature and rate constant of adsorption was determined. The pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order kinetic models were used to analyze the adsorption data. The results indicate that adsorption of lead and nickel ions on the sawdust of lam tree follow pseudo-first order kinetics. The intraparticle diffusion constants were calculated and it was found that intraparticle diffusion may be the only rate controlling step.

Keywords : *Cordia africana*, adsorption, nickel, lead, kinetics, sawdust.

Introduction

A huge increase in the use of heavy metals over the past few decades has resulted in an increased flux of metallic substances in aquatic environment¹. The heavy metals are released into the environment via waste effluents of many industries such as mining, metal plating, alloys paints, smelting, metal processing including metal plating and storage battery industries etc.². Unlike organic pollutants, the majority of which are susceptible to biological degradation, heavy metal ions do not degrade into harmless end-products³. Most of the metal ions are toxic to living organisms. Many metal ions have been classified as hazardous pollutants because of their potential toxicity to human health. In order to have pollution free environment, the toxic metal ions should be removed from wastewater before its disposal.

Several methods have been developed over the years to remove toxic metal ions from aqueous solution, which include chemical precipitation, membrane processes, electrofloatation, ion-exchange, reverse osmosis, solvent extraction and adsorption^{4,5}. The adsorption, both bio- and chemical-adsorption, has a definite edge over other techniques⁶ which are costly also. Various researchers have studied the adsorption of metal ions on a variety of adsorbents like oxides of silicon, manganese and aluminum, bentonite, hydrated titanium dioxide, modified silica

gel, polycarbonate filters, dithizone-anchored poly (EDGMA-HEMA) microbeads, resins, anionic microgel, bacterially oxidized manganese, ZnS, magnetite, pedogenic oxides, ferrihydrite, Brazilian oxisols, limestone, dolomite, lateritic minerals and agricultural by-products etc.^{5,6}. The need for safe and economical methods for the removal of toxic metal ions from contaminated waters has necessitated research for the development of low cost and sustainable adsorbents⁷⁻⁹. Thus various low cost agriculture/forest byproducts like bagasse agriculture waste¹⁰, rice husk¹¹, activated carbon from almond husk¹², pine bark¹³, modified Lalang leaf powder¹⁴, teawaste¹⁵, coir pith activated carbon¹⁶, nonliving algal biomass *Oedogonium* sp.¹⁷, *Rhizopus oligosporus*¹⁸, macrofungus (*Inonotus hispidus*) biomass¹⁹, *Ficus religiosa* leaves²⁰. Lichen (*Xanthoparmelia conspersa*) biomass²¹ and sawdust²²⁻²⁴ etc.

The first author of this study has reported the removal of lead and nickel ions from aqueous solution by adsorption on the sawdust of *Cordia africana*²⁵. In an extension of the work on sawdust of *Cordia africana*, the kinetics of the adsorption of lead and nickel ions on sawdust has been studied and presented in this paper.

Methods and materials :

Adsorbent : The sawdust of *Cordia africana* (lam tree)

was collected from a local saw mill in the vicinity of Jimma University, Jimma Ethiopia. It was sieved (50–60 mesh or 0.297–0.250 mm), washed several times with double-distilled water, dried in sunlight and then used for adsorption studies.

Chemicals : The stock solutions of Pb^{2+} (0.1 M) and Ni^{2+} (0.1 M) were prepared by dissolving $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively in double-distilled water. Both the salts were analytical grade reagents from E. Merck India Ltd. and were used as received. The stock solutions were further diluted with double-distilled water to required concentrations before use.

Adsorption experiments : The metal ion adsorption experiments were carried out using batch equilibrium technique. 1 g of sawdust was treated with a 50 ml aliquot of metal ion solution of desired concentration and shaken on a flask shaker for required time interval. After equilibration for the required time interval, the solution was filtered and the filtrate was analysed for the metal ion concentration. The concentration of the adsorbed metal ion was calculated by subtracting the concentration of the metal ion in the filtrate from the initial metal ion concentration. Metal ion concentration was determined by atomic adsorption spectrometry (Hitachi, Japan; Model 180-80).

Kinetic study : The change of amount of metal ion adsorbed as a function of shaking time (contact time) was analysed by taking 50 ml aliquots of metal ion solution (0.0025 M) in a number of stoppered conical flasks and shaking with 1 g of sawdust for different time intervals e.g. 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, 100, 110, 120 min. After the given time interval, the mixture was filtered and the filtrate was analysed for final metal ion concentration.

Results and discussion

The kinetic study shows that adsorption increases with increase in shaking time and reaches equilibrium after 50 min in case of Pb^{2+} and 70 min in case of Ni^{2+} attaining 64% and 52% adsorption of Pb^{2+} and Ni^{2+} respectively at 0.0025 M initial concentration of the metal ions. The adsorbent thus exhibits an uptake of 0.080 and 0.065 mmol/g of Pb^{2+} and Ni^{2+} respectively at 0.0025 M initial concentration of the metal ions. The results indicate that about 50% of the total Pb^{2+} adsorption takes place within first 10 min and thereafter the sorption rate de-

creases. Similarly, in case of Ni^{2+} about 50% of the total metal uptake takes place within first 20 min and thereafter the sorption rate decreases. The rapid rate of sorption of the metal ions in the initial period of the process may be due to a higher number of adsorption sites available on the bare surface of the adsorbent and the higher concentration gradient between the adsorbate in the solution and the adsorbate on the surface of the adsorbent. As the uptake of the metal ion progresses the concentration gradient between the metal ions in the solution and the metal ions on the adsorbent surface decreases and the number of the vacant adsorption sites on the adsorbent surface also decreases leading to a decrease in the sorption rate with time.

Adsorption kinetics is studied to calculate the rate of adsorption and to identify the rate-determining step. In the present study the adsorption data obtained from batch equilibrium experiments were analyzed by pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order kinetic models.

The pseudo-first order or Lagergren equation²⁶ is expressed as follows :

$$\frac{dq}{dt} = k_1(q_e - q) \quad (1)$$

where q_e and q are the amount of metal ion adsorbed (mmol/g) at equilibrium and at time t (min) respectively and k_1 is the rate constant of the pseudo-first order adsorption.

The linearized form of the equation becomes

$$\ln(q_e - q) = \ln q_e - k_1 t \quad (2)$$

A plot of $\ln(q_e - q)$ versus t should give a straight line with k_1 as slope and $\ln q_e$ as intercept.

The pseudo-second order equation²⁷ is expressed as

$$\frac{dq}{dt} = k_2(q_e - q)^2 \quad (3)$$

where k_2 is the rate constant of the pseudo-second order adsorption ($\text{g mmol}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$). The linearized form of the equation takes the following form

$$\frac{t}{q} = \frac{1}{k_2 q_e^2} + \frac{1}{q_e} t \quad (4)$$

A plot of t/q versus t should give a straight line and k_2 and q_e can be calculated from the slope and intercept.

Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 represent the pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order plots respectively, for the adsorption of lead and nickel ions. The pseudo-first order and

Fig. 1. Pseudo-first order kinetic plots for the adsorption of Pb^{2+} and Ni^{2+} on the sawdust of lam tree.

Fig. 2. Pseudo-second order kinetic plots for the adsorption of Pb^{2+} and Ni^{2+} on the sawdust of lam tree.

pseudo-second order kinetic constants are given in Table 1. It can be seen that the correlation coefficient r^2 for the pseudo-first order plots are higher than that for pseudo-second order plots. Moreover, the experimental q_e does not agree with the q_e calculated from the pseudo-second order kinetic plots whereas q_e value calculated

from the pseudo-first order plots are close to the experimental q_e in case of both the metal ions. Therefore, it can be said that the pseudo-first order kinetic model provides a good correlation for the adsorption of the lead and nickel ions on the sawdust of *Cordia africana*, in contrast to the pseudo-second order.

The rate constant for intraparticle diffusion (k_d) is given by the Weber and Morris equation²⁸,

$$q = k_d t^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

where q is the amount of the metal ion adsorbed (mmol/g) at time t (min). Plot of q versus $t^{1/2}$ for both the metal ions are shown in Fig. 3. Both the plots have the same features of a linear portion followed by a plateau. The linear portion is attributed to the intraparticle diffusion and the plateau to the equilibrium. Both the curves nearly pass through the origin, which indicates that intraparticle transport is perhaps the only rate-limiting step. The values of intraparticle diffusion rate constant, obtained from the slope of the linear portion of the curves, were found to be $9.91 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mmol g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1/2}$ and $8.61 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mmol g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1/2}$ for the lead and nickel ions respectively.

Fig. 3. Intraparticle-diffusion plots for the adsorption of Pb^{2+} and Ni^{2+} on the sawdust of lam tree.

Table 1. Pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order kinetic constants for the adsorption of Pb^{2+} and Ni^{2+} on the sawdust of lam tree

Ion	Pseudo-first order kinetics				Pseudo-second order kinetics			
	$q_{e, \text{exp}}^a$ (mmol/g)	$q_{e, \text{cal}}^a$ (mmol/g)	k_1 (min^{-1})	r^2	$q_{e, \text{exp}}^a$ (mmol/g)	$q_{e, \text{cal}}^a$ (mmol/g)	k_2 (min^{-1})	r^2
Pb^{2+}	0.080	0.076	0.0456	0.998	0.080	0.093	0.766	0.997
Ni^{2+}	0.065	0.069	0.0393	0.998	0.065	0.100	0.235	0.997

^aAt 0.0025 M initial concentration of the metal ions.

Conclusion :

The results indicate that adsorption of lead and nickel ions on the sawdust of *Cordia africana* follow pseudo-first order kinetics. The rate constant of the adsorption of lead and nickel ions were determined. The intraparticle diffusion constants were calculated and it was found that intraparticle diffusion is the only rate controlling step.

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